

Reactive dye-bath engineering of H₂O₂ for the protection of dye-waste, effluent management costs, total costs of the production, and nature

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H₂O₂ improves the absorbency and whitening effect of raw cotton fabric. But the H₂O₂ may decrease the strength of the cellulosic fabric. But the presence of H₂O₂ decreases the dyeing performance in dye-bath. But the H₂O₂ increases the dye-waste and dye-consumption in dye-bath. Proper management of H₂O₂ controlling and engineering in single bath dyeing process is a critical challenge to the textile engineers. To eliminate the dye-bath challenge and production hassle of single bath reactive dyeing of knitted cotton fabric; non-scoured, non-bleached, and non-dyed cotton fabric was scoured, bleached, and dyed in a single bath dyeing process. A reactive dyeing process was followed by 1% to 5% shading. The dye-bath engineering of H₂O₂ was analyzed and assessed for the cotton fabric dyeing with reactive dyes. The removal of H₂O₂ in dye-bath comparatively improved the dye evenness of dyed cotton fabric under the selected parameters of water quality. The shaded performance of dyed fabric was better for few times washing and draining process until the presence of H₂O₂ was not identified. Hence, the percentage of dye-waste minimization in reactive dye-bath was also comparatively assessed. Therefore; percentage of bleaching of fabric, uneven bleaching of fabric, remaining H₂O₂ in dye bath, and water parameters in single bath dyeing process should be critically monitored and controlled in the process of reactive dye-bath engineering and H₂O₂ engineering. The water parameters, chemical engineering, dye-bath engineering, and dye-bath chemicals in single bath dyeing process should be assessed for the protection of machine, dye-waste, effluent loads, quality of dyed fabric, effluent management costs, total costs of the production, and nature[1-7].

Acknowledgement

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Service type

- Chief researcher
- Independent researcher
- Self-funded researcher

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Professional service evidence as “dyeing officer (research and development)” of Mascom Composite Limited, Bangladesh

This research was also physically and commercially consulted and officially reported to the chairman and production department of Mascom Composite Limited in 2010-2011 as routine job requirement [8]. This research was consulted and officially reported to minimize the production cost to recover the salary compensation of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at Mascom Composite Limited.

Professional harassment

The symptom of family connection of Mr. Anam, Lab Incharge of Mascom Composite Limited, Surabari, Kashimpur-6591, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh was found in 2010-2011. The symptom of administrative misconduct of Mr. Shams Uddin Ahmed, Chairman was found in 2010-2011 [8-10].

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Author's biography since 1986

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